

Research Article

OnlyYourNotes: Development of an Encrypted Note-Taking App using Zero-Knowledge Architecture (ZKA) for Android Users with Hybrid Storage

Muhammad Nabil Mohd Sufian^{1,*}, and Shuib Basri²¹ muhammad_21000233@utp.edu.my; ORCID ID: 0000-0002-1736-4834

* Correspondence: muhammad_21000233@utp.edu.my; +60192685566.

Abstract: With the growing reliance on digital note-taking apps, users frequently store sensitive information such as bank details, passwords, and personal data in these platforms. However, concerns persist regarding the security and privacy of stored data, as traditional note-taking apps often rely on server-managed authentication and encryption keys, introducing potential vulnerabilities. In response, this project introduces OnlyYourNotes, a secure note-taking application that implements Zero-Knowledge architecture (ZKA) with hybrid storage. The focus is on enabling digital notes users securely store notes where only the user can decrypt and access their notes, even the developers or cloud service providers cannot view the contents. By utilizing AES-256 encryption and client-side encryption techniques, the system secures user data both in transit and at rest. The encryption key is managed locally using flutter_secure_storage, eliminating the need for server-side key management. The app includes features such as adding, editing, and exporting encrypted notes, with a user-friendly interface. A minimal authentication mechanism is implemented to demonstrate secure access without server intervention. Testing covers functionality, encryption correctness, key persistence, and usability. This project addresses rising concerns about data privacy in personal productivity apps and serves as a lightweight, practical implementation of ZKA for mobile environments.

Keywords: Secure Note-Taking; Zero-Knowledge; Client-Side Encryption; AES-256; Data Privacy; Key Management; Mobile Security.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In today's digital landscape, note-taking applications are essential tools for organizing sensitive information such as passwords, financial records and confidential work-related data. While these platforms offer convenience and cross-device accessibility many do still rely on centralized authentication systems and cloud-based storage which makes them vulnerable to data breaches, insider threats and unauthorized access. Real-world incidents emphasize the severity of these vulnerabilities. The CVE-2023-34362 vulnerability in MOVEit, a managed file transfer software that led to a large-scale data breach impacting thousands of organizations and nearly 100 million individuals (CISA,2023). Attackers exploited an SQL injection flaw on business database. In another case, it was revealed that Evernote employees had access to unencrypted user notes stored on their servers which contradict their security assurances (Tung, 2020). In 2023, Microsoft OneNote became a vector for malware attacks where cybercriminals embedded malicious scripts in unencrypted note files and spread them via phishing emails (Ahmed, 2023). These examples reflect the broader risks associated with centralized data storage and insufficient encryption practices. To address these challenges, the scope of this study focuses on the research and development of OnlyYourNotes a secure note-taking application that

leverages Zero-Knowledge Architecture (ZKA) and a hybrid storage model. Unlike conventional systems that store keys or credentials on external servers, OnlyYourNotes manages encryption keys locally. This ensures that only the user can access their encrypted data. Notes are protected using AES-256 encryption and stored locally with optional encrypted backups distributed across decentralized cloud services.

The application is designed to serve both digital natives and digital immigrants. While digital natives those born into the digital era are often assumed to be tech-savvy, research suggests that access to technology does not necessarily equate to secure usage (Prensky, 2001). Digital immigrants, by contrast, may struggle with adopting new technology or adapting to modern digital environments (Vodanovich et al., 2010). Therefore, OnlyYourNotes aims to offer a balance of strong security and intuitive usability to meet the needs of both demographics. It targets individuals and professionals who store sensitive content such as passwords, medical records or legal documents and such that require an accessible but robust privacy-first solution. The methodology followed during development phase is presented in Section 2.0. In Section 3.0 shows findings of how the implementation of ZKA solved existing problems with detailed discussion.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

2.1 Development Method and Tools

Given the structured and security-centric nature of this project, the Waterfall methodology is adopted within the Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC) framework. This linear and sequential model is well-suited for projects requiring meticulous planning and clear documentation particularly when implementing complex security mechanisms. The Waterfall model consists of several key phases: Requirement, Analysis, System Design, Implementation, Testing and Maintenance. Such a rigid structure is essential for integrating advanced features like AES-256 encryption, client-side encryption and key derivation.

Figure 1. System Architecture Diagram of the OnlyYourNotes

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2.2 Systems Interaction

The use case diagram illustrates how users interact with the Zero-Knowledge Architecture (ZKA)-Based Secure Note System. Key functions include signing up to generate a local Master Key, creating, editing, viewing and deleting encrypted notes, and securely backing up or restoring them via cloud providers like Google Drive, Dropbox and OneDrive. All encryption and decryption occur on the user’s device to make sure no plaintext data is exposed externally. This architecture maintains strict privacy by enforcing zero-knowledge principles and preventing unauthorized access.

Figure 2. Use Case Diagram of the OnlyYourNotes Apps

2.3 Logical Flow of System

The system flowcharts illustrate three key processes in the app: user authentication (login or sign-up), secure note creation with AES-256 encryption and optional cloud backup, and the deletion process that removes notes from both local and cloud storage. These diagrams represent the structured flow of user interactions and data handling to ensure security and privacy throughout the app.

Figure 3. User Log In Flow

Figure 4. User Creates & Encrypts Notes Flow

Figure 5. Notes Deletion Flow

3. FINDINGS

3.1 Key Capabilities of the App

This section shows the final implementation of the OnlyYourNotes secure note-taking application. The developed app offers essential capabilities, including adding, editing, and deleting notes, all securely stored using Hive. It features client-side AES-256 encryption, secure key management via Flutter Secure Storage, and supports both offline encrypted backups and encrypted cloud backups with Google Drive. Its offline-first architecture ensures reliable access even without internet connectivity.

Figure 6. Splash Screen of the OnlyYourNotes App

Figure 7. Main Dashboard (Filled)

Figure 8. Database Debug Info Page (with data stored)

Figure 9. Edit Note page

Figure 10. Google Drive Cloud Backups page

Figure 11. Local Backups page

3.2 System Data Flow Findings

The data flow diagram showcases the secure encryption workflow of the note-taking app. When users create or edit notes, content is encrypted using AES-256 before storage, ensuring plaintext never enters the database. The secret key is stored securely via Flutter Secure Storage and Android Keystore. Encrypted notes (ciphertext) are stored in Hive and decrypted only locally when viewed. All processes occur on-device, with no key exposure to servers. Encrypted notes can also be exported as JSON files for backup, maintaining data confidentiality even outside the app.

Figure 12. Encryption Data Flow Diagram

4. DISCUSSION

This section discusses the performance of the cloud-based export and import functionality using the Google Drive API which allows users to back up and restore their encrypted notes securely. Google Cloud Console metrics were reviewed to validate the system’s API performance, latency and reliability during data operations.

Methods

Method ↑	Requests	Errors	Avg latency	99th percentile latency ?
google.apps.drive.v3.DriveFiles.Create	14	0	0.55 seconds	3.901 seconds
google.apps.drive.v3.DriveFiles.Get	20	0	0.445 seconds	3.775 seconds
google.apps.drive.v3.DriveFiles.List	12	0	0.267 seconds	0.514 seconds

Figure 13. Google Drive Methods-Level Statistics Flow Diagram

Details from Figure 13 indicates that the 99th percentile latency which translates into a sense of worst-case performance under load for “google.apps.drive.v3.DriveFiles.Create” will be 3.901 seconds, indicating one or two longer delays in an unusual usage condition.

Name	↓ Requests	Errors (%)	Latency, median (ms)	Latency, 95% (ms)
Google Drive API	46	0	238	1,939

Figure 14. Summary of Google Drive API & Services

Overall, based on monitoring through Google Cloud Console, the application recorded a total of 46 requests made to the Google Drive API during the export and import operations.

These requests were successfully processed with a 0% error rate, indicating a highly stable and reliable integration between the app and the cloud service. The system achieved a median latency of 238 milliseconds which demonstrates responsive performance suitable for real-time user interactions. Additionally, it is worth noting that the 95th percentile latency was recorded at 1,939 milliseconds this accounts for peak operation delays but still falls within an acceptable range for cloud-based storage operations.

The zero-error rate confirms that no interruptions or failures occurred during API usage reinforcing the robustness of the current implementation. The median latency being below 300 milliseconds means that users can expect near-instantaneous response times when performing export or import actions to or from Google Drive. These performance indicators reflect that OnlyYourNotes has a well-optimized connection to cloud services for users to enjoy the principles of a smooth and secure user experience.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the OnlyYourNotes mobile application was developed to demonstrate a secure privacy-focused note-taking solution based on Zero-Knowledge Architecture (ZKA). The system implements client-side encryption mechanisms to ensure that sensitive user data remains inaccessible to both developers and external service providers. The application successfully integrates AES-256

encryption for securing note content with encryption keys stored locally using flutter_secure_storage and protected by Android Keystore. All encryption and decryption operations occur exclusively on the user's device. The application supports secure offline storage using the Hive database and includes functionality for encrypted export to cloud services such as Google Drive. These capabilities enhance usability while maintaining the integrity and confidentiality of user data during transmission and backup.

The project has successfully achieved its objective of developing a secure note-taking application where only the user can access the contents of their notes. The implementation confirms the practicality of integrating Zero-Knowledge principles into mobile applications. By eliminating server-side key management and maintaining a fully client-controlled encryption workflow. OnlyYourNotes offers a lightweight, scalable and privacy-preserving solution. This work contributes to the broader field of secure mobile computing and highlights the applicability of Zero-Knowledge-based approaches in personal data management.

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